

FEATURES OF PSYLLIUM EXTRACTION IN THE PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY

Koilybaeva M.K., Babakova A.S

Kazakh National Medical University of S.D. Asfendiyarov,
koilybayeva.m@kaznmu.kz, +7 707 262 90 91; babakova.asev@list.ru, + 7 708 841 62 85
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10681944>

Abstract: In recent years, synthetic drugs have been widely replaced by medicinal herbs and extracts due to their small number of undesirable and extensive beneficial effects. The leaves and seeds of the plantain are widely used in folk medicine for various purposes, including the treatment of a wide range of diseases and disorders such as respiratory complications and lesions of the digestive system

Key words: plantain, pharmacy, extraction agent, plantago major, antimicrobial action, biologically active substances, extraction agent.

Topicality of topic: The importance of plantain extract may be related to its wide range of beneficial properties and use in medicine, cosmetology and the food industry. At the first relevance Plantain has anti-inflammatory, wound healing, antimicrobial and antiviral properties. Plantain extract can be used to treat various skin problems such as burns, wounds, abrasions and acne. It can also help with diseases of the respiratory system, allergies, gastroenterological problems, elimination of constipation and reduction of inflammatory processes.

You can use plantain extract contains many active ingredients that help improve skin condition, fight acne, pigmentation, severe dryness and have a rejuvenating effect. Plantain can be used as a part of creams, masks and hair products.

Finally relevance of plantain extract can be in the production of functional food products and additives such as beverages, juices, syrups, medical teas and even confectionery. In such products, psyllium extract can provide antioxidant protection, strengthen the immune system and improve digestion.

Object of investigation: To study the pharmacological properties of psyllium extract to determine its potential use in the treatment of various diseases or conditions.

Methods of investigation: The collection of vegetable raw materials of plantain was carried out in June-July 2010 in places of growth no closer than 40 km from the location of industrial enterprises. Drying and storage of the harvested plant was carried out according to the existing rules. The study of the biochemical composition is given by Fluorate—02—2m. The content of the latest revealed. They were measured on an atomic absorption spectrometer with electrothermal atomization "MGA-915" and using a fluorimetric plant were carried out according to the State Pharmacopoeia of the USSR and the corresponding GOST standards. The content of extractive substances, flavonoids, carotenoids, ascorbic acid, tannins, as well as the amount of micro- and macronutrients were determined in the plant. Considering that a significant number of enterprises of the mining and metallurgical complex are located in the East Kazakhstan region, causing man-made environmental pollution, it is important to determine the content of heavy metals in the plant. To study the antimicrobial properties of the plant, an infusion was obtained: aqueous, 40° and 70° ethyl alcohol, 3% and 5% aqueous solution of ammonia according to generally accepted methods. These extractants are most often used in the preparation of phytopreparations. The antibacterial effect of the infusions was determined by the method of serial dilutions in a liquid nutrient medium - BCH. The test objects were staphylococci and streptococci isolated from the secretion of inflamed mammary gland. The study of the large plantain growing in Eastern Kazakhstan showed that the plant has a high content of flavonoids, polysaccharides, ascorbic acid, carotenoids, various macro and microelements. The greatest extractive effect was found in solutions of ammonia. This plant has

an antimicrobial effect against microorganisms isolated from the secretions of inflamed mammary glands of cows. There was no increased content of heavy metals in the plant. The data obtained make it possible to use plantain large to expand veterinary use.

Main results: When studying biologically active substances of plantain, it was found that 3 and 5% aqueous solutions of ammonia have the greatest extractive activity. The plant contains significant amounts of tannins, carotenoids, ascorbic acid, flavonoids and polysaccharides.

For the qualitative determination of biologically active substances and the features of psyllium extraction, the absorption spectra of extracts were studied. It was found that peaks of 355-370 nm confirm the presence of tannins in the plant and a wide range of flavonoids — multiple peaks of 320-460 nm. Flavonoids are completely extracted with a solution of ammonia, and the absorption spectra of alcohol extracts have absorption bands corresponding to phenolic compounds and chlorophyll (510-670 nm). Ammonia extracts a greater amount of baicalin and cinnaroside, and alcohol extracts rutin and lutein.

The study of inorganic compounds has shown the presence of a wide range of macro and microelements in plantain

Conclusions: The study of the large plantain growing in Eastern Kazakhstan showed that the plant has a high content of flavonoids, polysaccharides, ascorbic acid, carotenodes, various macro and microelements. The greatest extractive effect was found in solutions of ammonia. This plant has an antimicrobial effect against microorganisms isolated from the secretions of inflamed mammary glands of cows. There was no increased content of heavy metals in the plant. The data obtained make it possible to use plantain bolshoy more widely in veterinary practice

References:

1. Putyrsky I.N., Prokhorov V.N. Universal encyclopedia of medicinal plants. — Minsk: Book House; Moscow: Makhaon, 2000 — 656 p.
2. Kovalev V.F., Volkov I.V., Violin B.V. and others. Antibiotics, sulfonamides and nitrofurans in veterinary medicine: handbook.
3. Sosnina, S.A. Types of plantain: the content of active substances / S.A. Sosnina, G.I. Oleshko, L.G. Pecherskaya et al. // Pharmacy. - 2008. - No.8. - pp. 21-24
4. Long C., Moulis C., Stanislas E., Fourasté E. L'Aucuboside et the Catalpol Dans les Feuilles the *Plantago lanceolata* L., *Plantago major* L. et *Plantago media* L. // Journal de Pharmacie de Belgique. 1995. V. 50. P. 484-488.